

Role of Technology in Management education in India

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Abstract:- The advancement of Technology has impacted everything and everyone around us. From computers to smart phones and their role in education, the journey has been very illuminating. Soon, mind hacking devices would be taking the position of our books and notebooks. No doubt, the human brain is also evolving and getting sharper day by day, the result of which is a 5-year old kid can operate smart phones. When it comes to education, India bags 92nd position among 145 countries. India must work on the rate and level of education provided to the management students. Moreover, it must ensure that every student gets quality education. However, now people are very much interested in getting their technology based education as they have understood the importance of it. It is common to have a large computer screen instead of a whiteboard and tablets instead of notebooks to take down the notes. We are not totally there but we are walking towards it.

Keywords:- Smart Phones, Human Brain, Computer Screen, Quality Education and Note Books.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology is changing every aspect of our lives, and education is one of the most important sectors that need to be modernized and advanced leading to the overall growth of the institution. Meanwhile, it is also essential that institutions must understand the right usage and importance of educational technology. Technology these days is far more than digital whiteboards, learning management systems, and such technological tools. So which technology are you using in your institution to be in the technological touch? Let's discuss some of the important technologies and their benefits for education institutions.

Education Digital Transformation and Innovation

Source: Gartner
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Fig 1 Education Digital Transformation and Innovation

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

- To know different technologies used in education.
- To know the role of technology in education.
- To know the importance of the technology.

➤ *Sources of the Data*

The information is being collected by the secondary sources. such as from the websites, books and journals.

II. DIFFERENT TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR BENEFITS IN EDUCATION

➤ *ERP for seamless academic & administrative workings*

Various types of educational technology are evolving in the modern world that are supporting institutions, but ERP is the only and one of the leading technologies that provide complete automation of all the academic and administrative activities in the institution. It can manage all the operations like admission, enrollment, fee, hostel, library, transportation, examination, result declaration.. A good ERP system even provides a simple and coding-free portal with a mobile application through which all the stakeholders like students, faculty, parents, administrators can manage their tasks effectively.

➤ *SIS for a seamless relationship between students and faculty*

Students are one the most important stakeholders of an institution, institutions need to opt for techniques through which students can focus on their studies directly instead of indulging in day-to-day operations and tasks. A student information system is one of the leading technologies that is helping various institutions to create a systematic workflow of all the operations associated with a student. Having a student information system, institutions can attain and fill admission forms using the portal or mobile application.They can even get their enrollment numbers; can attain a systematic flow of timetable, examination details, and even the results. Institutions also get access to students' activities from anywhere and anytime starting from their attendance to all other daily activities that are triggered for the overall growth of students and the institution.

➤ *Immersive learning for the enhanced learning experience*

In the modern era of technology, learning and teaching are not only restricted to classrooms and textbooks. The students of today's generation expect a more advanced and immersive experience that can solve their curiosity with practical solutions.

Immersive learning provides students with real-time experiences created through augmented, VR/AR reality. These real-time experiences can transfer students virtually to the planet and help them eat up all the information to satisfy their curiosity and hunger in the best manner.

➤ *Gamification for fun, and modern learning*

Games have always been the first choice of any age group, Technology is changing in every aspect and now using different technological games classrooms can be personified to make lessons more interactive and understandable along with boosting participation, encouragement, and collaboration.

Technology subjugated every aspect of the social order and is now the life and blood of modern society and will be for a long time to come. It will re-develop again and again to cater to the new needs of changing society. The iGen – those born in or after 1995, cannot imagine life without technology.

With the advent of technological innovations across industries, the education sector turns out to be the most influenced. In-fact, technology has been playing a prominent role at the forefront of education ever since learning and development came into being, right from carving symbols and figures on walls of caves, to Gurukul education where the students were taught the use of the technology prevailing then, to using of artificial intelligence (AI) and virtual reality (VR).

Modern technology has completely reshaped the entire education system. The digitally empowered classrooms over the internet have made education available to each and everyone who wants to learn across the world, anytime, any subject and anywhere. There is no limit to the strength of the classroom. Unlike physical classrooms that are limited to a maximum of sixty students, any number of students can access the virtual classrooms. When it comes to learning, there is an unlimited amount of knowledge available at no cost to an economically viable price.

In today's rapidly progressing world of modernization and digitalization, the introduction of technology in every field or sector is becoming crucial. Exciting technological advancements are happening every day which are benefiting humans in every aspect of their lives. Education is one such field that is welcoming technology adoption positively.

With the Covid-19 pandemic affecting people across the world, schools were closed as part of lockdown measures to contain the virus, thereby disrupting academics. Educational institutions engage virtually with students and teachers in the form of ICTs to continue with academics.

III. SOME WAYS TECHNOLOGY IS BEING USED IN EDUCATION

➤ *Neural Education*

Neuroscience is the scientific study of the nervous system, including neuroanatomy, neurobiology, neurochemistry, neurophysiology, and neuropharmacology, and its applications in psychology, psychiatry, and neurology. Neural education offers a deeper understanding of the brain's amazing capacity. It is a learning method that is aligned with the way in which the brain processes information. It optimizes

the learning experience by creating a positive mood through self-directed learning, facilitates the brain to embed new learning in existing knowledge, and enhances information recall speed for Long Term Potentiation.

➤ *VR Technology*

Virtual reality and augmented reality are new technological advancements that bring a different facet to the classroom. Using VR gear, students can visit remote areas and encounter ancient civilizations. This is a fascinating addition to the learning process, where one can gain close experiences that are not possible in reality. Augmented reality users get to experience a complete real-world environment blended with digital elements. The use of these two technologies has been shown to positively affect student engagement.

➤ *Robotics*

Technology helps students get comfortable with the modern world through problem-solving as well as facilitates learning. Robotics introduces students to all branches of the STEM system (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics). STEM learning demands critical thinking and problem solving and, through robotics, students can learn to approach the knowledge they gain with a solution-oriented approach.

IV. HERE ARE 3 WAYS TECHNOLOGY PLAYS A VITAL ROLE IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

➤ *Promotes An Effective Educational System*

Undoubtedly, technology encourages the overall development of students. Technology is an effective way to promote a healthy educational system worldwide. The most important role of technology in education makes learning more accessible, exciting, and enjoyable. The development of technological advancements in education leads to enhanced knowledge and skills of students.

➤ *Technology Helps Students Learn Better*

Research has proved that digital learning technology helps most students improve their academic grades. Apart from academic improvement, with the help of technology-based learning, students can learn more from a variety of resources without depending on teachers.

➤ *Boosts Communication And Collaboration*

The introduction of technology has greatly improved the level of communication and collaboration. Technology also boosted communication and collaboration between teachers, parents, and students.

The introduction of technological devices and programmes at an early age makes it much easier for students to adopt new methods. Technology is a great way to prepare children for the future and the challenges that they may face. With a great asset, students will be able to overcome difficulties and put their skills to better use. Technology has

many advantages, but it cannot beat mankind as human beings are always required for decision-making, supervision, and ideation.

V. IMPERATIVE ROLES OF TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Here the authors cited 10 important roles of technology in education for students as well as parents and teachers, have a glance –

➤ *Promotes Effective Educational system*

Undoubtedly, since technology is introduced in the classroom, it encourages the overall growth of students. Technology is a robust process to promote a healthy educational system worldwide. The Most Important roles of technology in education make learning more accessible, exciting and enjoyable. The development of technological advancements in education leads to enhance knowledge and skills of students.

➤ *Technology Helps Students Learn Much and Better*

Digital learning technology helps most students improve their grades. Furthermore, through technology-based E-learning, students can learn more and better from different resources without depending on an institution or an instructor.

➤ *Improvise better Communication and Collaboration*

We all know that the existence of technology has improved communication and collaboration to a better level. Likewise, Educational technology also boosted communication and collaboration between teachers and students and students/ parents, teachers/parents, and peers.

Teachers can interact with students to clear their doubts and make e-learning more effective. Technology enables one-on-one interaction in the classroom online.

➤ *Provide Teachers More Resources*

Educational technology provides teachers plenty of e-learning tools like Gamification, smart boards etc. Through Advanced modern technology of education, teachers can use various digital tools to magnify learning opportunities for students.

E-learning solution technologies enable teachers to improve their teaching skills. From technology, teachers can instruct well through video lessons, micro learning, attractive info graphics etc. Moreover, teachers can engage the students by delivering online tests and different courses.

➤ *Learning At Own Pace*

The important roles of technology in education are to students as they can learn at any time and from anywhere. With the technology-based E-learning process, one can study in their comfort zone. Students can play, pause and re-watch complex topics using online educational applications until the concept is clear.

➤ *More Opportunities for Online Project-Based Learning*

Most schools are opting now for online Project-Based Learning instead of wasting time on pen paper-based projects. Technological solutions have also made Project-Based learning much more accessible and convenient for students. Now, one can create presentations using Google Classroom, Google Docs, PPT and Slides, etc. Through online Project-Based Learning, students use their skills and knowledge up to the next level to complete an assignment.

➤ *Personalized Learning Opportunities*

The importance Of Technology in Education is not just limited to efficient learning, but students can also have their personalized learning opportunities. Availability of more resources/ material 24*7 to students allows them to personalize learning better. We all know that not all students have the same learning frequency; thus, personalized learning is considered. Personalize learning is also known as self-paced learning, which can help individuals optimize the quantity of material according to their capability.

➤ *Efficient Problem Solving Stuff*

Well, studying without having any doubts can be possible only through modern intelligent classes. Video modules of every concept help each of you to cut out the doubts. So, if any problem arises in any topic, just go through Problem Solving material and clear all doubts.

➤ *Better Understanding through Graphics*

Technology has evaluated the learning process through video graphics, which helps the human mind understand the concept faster and remember it for a long time. This can be only possible because of the visual information system. Using technology in education, students can retain knowledge by 25% to 60%. Using technology like gamification, mobile learning, micro learning, visual graphics etc. students can experience fun and learning at the same time and keep engaged with their studies.

➤ *Save Time and Money*

With the availability of more study material via E-learning technology, the student can spend less money on other materials. Even nowadays, many schools are more emphasizing on buying online study material, which is cheaper and convenient for storage. Teachers can save time and money by teaching students via advanced educational, technological systems like augmented reality and virtual reality programs free of cost online and helps one to learn and understand faster.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this present scenario technology should be used by all the management institutions. It is mandatory and essence from the side of management. As per the changes all the teaching faculty should update themselves by adopting technology while importing education. Quality education leads to better future as well as better opportunities.

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